

Evaluation of Socioeconomic costs of Road Traffic Crashes on Victims in Federal Capital Territory Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs) have become a significant public health crisis in Nigeria, with 60,155 crashes and 30,105 fatalities between 2011 and 2015. Survivors suffer enduring trauma and lifelong disabilities and become liabilities to their families and communities. The psychological burden is particularly pronounced in African societies with kinship systems. This study evaluates the socioeconomic costs of RTCs on victims and families in Abuja. Data was collected from six general hospitals in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT), focusing on hospitalized RTC victims and their relatives. A total of 121 victims and relatives sampled were determined from the average monthly admission of 178 RTC victims across the selected hospitals using Krejcie and Morgan's sampling formula. Descriptive statistics were utilised to analyse the respondents' socioeconomic characteristics and impact, and both the Human Capital and Willingness-To-Pay (WTP) approaches were employed to quantify the economic burden of RTCs. The study reveals that male victims constitute 71% of the sample, with a predominant middle-age group of 36%. The socioeconomic impact is profound, particularly among lower-income households, where limited financial resources hinder access to necessary medical care. The estimated socioeconomic costs of RTCs in the FCT for 2022 was approximately ₦534.9 billion (around US\$1.2 billion), primarily driven by productivity losses and long-term care costs. 58.7% of victims experienced severe impacts from crashes. The study shows the need for targeted policy reforms and enhanced support systems to alleviate the financial and psychological impacts on RTC victims and households. The findings are vital for informing interventions and improving road safety measures across Nigeria.

Keywords: Disease burden, Fatalities, Human Capital, Socioeconomic costs, Road Traffic Crashes, Willingness-To-Pay

1 INTRODUCTION

Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs) have emerged as an important public health crisis in Nigeria, characterized by both the number of incidents and resultant fatalities. During the five-year period 2011-2015, Nigeria recorded 60,155 road traffic crashes with 30,105 fatalities (FRSC, 2016). Global efforts, particularly by governmental and research entities, have been directed toward mitigating the incidence of RTCs, owing to profound social and economic conse-

quences as disease burden (Takako, 2019). The Federal Road Safety Corps in Nigeria established strategic goals in 2015 which aimed for 20% reduction in RTCs and 30% decrease in fatalities. According to WHO Global Status Report (2018), road traffic crash is the world's fifth leading cause of mortality and morbidity which rank among the top three causes of death for individuals aged 5 to 44, leading to the declaration of 2021-2030 as Decade of Action for Road Safety (WHO, 2021).

Despite initiatives, there remains a pronounced inadequate of comprehensive studies capturing the full extent of impacts that RTCs impose on survivors and relatives, especially within developing countries. Sung and Rios (2015) delved into the dearth of systematic surveys examining the effects of road crashes on affected households, emphasizing the inherent challenges in tracing victims for research purposes. Huang *et al.*, (2016) further examined that investigations into the repercussions of fatal crashes on victims' families have not been adequately prioritized, with the requisite data often either unavailable or difficult to quantify in the context of developing nations.

The aftermath of RTCs extends far beyond the immediate loss of life; it inflicts enduring trauma on survivors and families. Survivors may endure lifelong disabilities, becoming successive liabilities to families and communities. This psychological burden is pronounced in African societies where kinship system dictates familial responsibilities. Eke (2015) stated that the exacerbation of issues in such nations is inadequate of robust social security services. Where there is good social policy in place, for instance, countries involved among others, South Korea illustrated how effective social policies—like comprehensive auto-insurance covering medical expenses, rehabilitation costs, and indemnity for death—can mitigate the adverse effects of RTCs. The average compensation amounts in 1999 for automobile fatalities in South Korea were estimated at \$53,600 and \$2,330 for injuries alone (Yang and Kim, 2003).

One of the critical obstacles in accurately evaluating the socioeconomic impacts of RTCs is the insufficient collection of relevant data. Therefore, ascertaining the tangible pain and suffering inflicted by RTCs poses a significant challenge. The European Transport Safety Council (2007) developed various scales to gauge these effects which are categorised into those based on clinical assessments and those relying on self-reported evaluations from victims. Huang (2024) utilised a cross-sectional survey approach in Taiwan, focusing on victims and their families. The findings indicate that the actual costs associated with severe traffic crashes extend beyond individual medical recovery and replacement of physical losses, encompassing broader psycho-social costs and adverse consequences experienced by victims' kin. Additionally, Mohammad and Abdelmageed (2010) assessed a dual methodology based on the Human Capital approach in Egypt, estimating the average costs associated with fatalities, injuries, and property damage. The comprehensive framework incorporated multiple dimensions: the economic costs of lost productivity, medical expenses, and quality-of-life losses, while likewise accounting for associated vehicle repair costs and property damages. This provided a stratification of crash costs based on severity levels, illustrating a nuanced understanding of the varying impacts of RTCs.

An alternative approach, known as Willingness-To-Pay (WTP), was posited by Donário *et al.*, (2012) as an ex-ante method for assessing the economic burden of RTCs. WTP reflects the monetary value individuals assign to reducing risk of being involved in crashes, effectively encompassing numerous indirect social costs experienced by communities—ranging from lost income to diminishing quality of life stemming from fear of potential crashes. According to Donário *et al.* (2012), the Human Capital approach permits the utilisation of temporal data across various periods; the WTP approach relies on time-specific datasets and, thus, adopted the Human Capital methodology in their Portuguese analysis, citing the requisite dependency on nationwide surveys to ascertain the economic costs associated with crashes. This study therefore, examined Human Capital and WTP approaches to evaluate the socioeconomic costs and impacts of road traffic crashes on victims and relatives in Abuja.

2 THE STUDY AREA

The Federal Capital Territory (FCT) Administration was established on February 3, 1976, with Abuja designated as the capital city of Nigeria, strategically situated in the central region of the country. Geographically, the FCT is

situated on latitude of 8°50'N and a longitude of 7°10'E, bordered to the North by Kaduna State, to the Southwest by Kogi State, to the West by Niger State, and to the East by Nasarawa State (Uhegbu and Tight, 2021). The FCT encompasses an area of 7,135 km² (approximately 2,824 square miles) and has witnessed significant socioeconomic changes over the years. As per the National Population Commission, the population in 2016 was recorded at 1,460,239. By 2022, projections indicated a population of approximately 3,067,457, with future estimates suggesting growth to around 4,026,000, reflecting an annual growth rate of 4.84% (UN World Urbanisation Prospect, 2018). FCT Abuja's rapid urbanisation has precipitated a range of urban challenges, including traffic congestion, housing scarcity, inadequate public transport infrastructure, and increasing environmental pollution. The urban sprawl is anticipated to extend beyond the current FCT boundaries, encroaching into adjacent states such as Nasarawa, Kaduna, and Niger. The expansion is likely to integrate neighbouring towns, including Suleja, into Abuja's socioeconomic framework, thereby transforming the regional dynamics.

Figure 1 FCT Abuja

Authors' Work, 2025

3 METHODOLOGY

The population frame for the study comprises RTC victims admitted to Accident and Emergency Units alongside accompanying relatives at the General Hospitals in the FCT. The FCT is home to fifteen General Hospitals distributed across the six Area Councils with a total of 1153 bed spaces. There is an average number of 417 RTC patients admitted per month with a total of 136 bed spaces in the Accident and Emergency Units.. To ensure a representative sample, a random number assessment was employed to select six General Hospitals

in the FCT and only RTC victims receiving treatment and supported relatives in those hospitals were included in the analysis. Utilising the Krejcie and Morgan's sampling formula, a sample size of 121 was extracted from the average monthly admission of 178 RTC victims across the selected Hospitals. Therefore, a total of 121 structured questionnaires were administered to RTC victims in the selected General Hospitals and another set of 121 questionnaires were also administered alongside to relatives of RTC victims in the same Hospitals. The non-probabilistic hybrid sampling technique of convenience and purposive method was adopted in the administration of the questionnaires.

The selected hospitals were General Hospital Kuje, General Hospital Abaji, General Hospital Kwali, General Hospital Bwari, General Hospital Zuba and General Hospital Wuse as seen in table 1. The administration of the questionnaires took four (4) months for the survey, as the results were analysed in frequencies and percentages.

Table 1: Sample sizes of RTC Victims in General Hospitals

S/N	Hospital	Average Number of RTC victims Admitted per Month	RTC Sample distribution per Hospital
1	General Hospital Abaji	31	21
2	General Hospital Wuse	29	20
3	General Hospital Kuje	25	17
4	General Hospital Bwari	33	22
5	General Hospital Kwali	27	18
6	General Hospital Zuba	33	23
Total		178	121

Source: Authors' Work based on FCT Hospital Management Board Records (2025)

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Socioeconomic background of Respondents

The socioeconomic characteristics of RTC victims are crucial for formulating effective programmatic and policy interventions that cut across all socioeconomic strata in order to mitigate the consequences of such traffic crashes. Table 2 summarises an overview of RTC victims in FCT based on gender, age, and ethnicity. The

result reveals significant gender disparities, with males constituting 71% of victims compared to 29% females. The high traffic crash rates among males is attributed to driving behaviour and increased exposure to driving environment than female counterpart.

The age distribution indicates that the most affected group was individuals aged 31-40 years (36%), followed by those aged 41-50 years (27%). This portrays the fact that 36% of middle-aged drivers, who often engaged in work-related travel and family responsibilities, may be more prone to risky driving behaviour. Similarly, ethnic representation among victims shows that 34% were Hausa, 26.4% Igbo, and 21.5% Yoruba, indicating potential regional disparities in the study area. Therefore, recognizing these ethnic dynamics is vital for developing culturally sensitive interventions aimed at enhancing road safety awareness.

The result further reveals that most RTC victims resided outside the FCT (70.2%), while 29.8% resided within the FCT (see table 2).

This indicates that individuals commuting into the FCT face the risk of being involved in a road traffic crash than those residing in the FCT. This may be due to complexity of road infrastructure and inadequate of drivers' experiences in road traffic signs and regulations in the study area.

4.2 Monthly Income of RTC Victims

The income distribution of RTC victims provides insights into the socioeconomic implications of RTCs in FCT. Table 3 reveals the largest group (36.3%) falls within the income level of ₦40,500 to ₦50,000, followed by victims with income range of ₦50,500 to ₦60,000 (24%). A significant proportion of RTC victims (5.7% earned less than ₦30,000 and 14% earned between ₦30,500 and ₦40,000) indicates that many individuals affected by road traffic crashes were from low-income backgrounds. The socioeconomic segment is particularly vulnerable to the economic repercussions of road traffic crashes, as limited financial resources can hinder access to adequate medical care and rehabilitation services.

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	71	86
	Female	29	35
Age	Below 10 years	2	
	11–20 years	9	7
	21–30 years	24	20
	31–40 years	43	36
	41–50 years	33	27
	51–60 years	8	
	61 years and above	2	
Ethnicity	Hausa	41	34.0
	Igbo	32	26.4
	Yoruba	26	21.5
	Others	22	18.1
Place of Residence	Within FCT	36	29.8
	Outside FCT	85	70.2

Source: Authors' Field Work (2025)

Table 3: Monthly Income of RTC Victims

Married	34	28.3
Divorced	8	6.7
Separated	13	10.8

4.3 Educational Level of RTC Victims

The distribution in Table 4 reveals that 43.8% of RTC victims had completed secondary education, while only 28.1% had tertiary qualifications, primary education (12.4%) and others (15.7%). This result reveals the educational status among RTC victims which reflects broader socioeconomic challenges faced by individuals. Those with lower educational attainment are often at a disadvantaged in terms of economic opportunities, which can exacerbate the financial burdens and economic instability placed on families affected by road traffic injuries, as this has long-term implications for community development and public health systems.

Income	Frequency	%
Less than ₦30,000	7	5.7
₦30,500–₦40,000	17	14.0
₦40,500–₦50,000	44	36.3
₦50,500–₦60,000	29	24.0
₦60,500–₦70,000	14	11.5
More than ₦70,000	10	8.5
Total	121	100.0

Widow	6	5.2
Educational Status		
Primary (FSLC)	15	12.4
Secondary school	53	43.8
Tertiary school	34	28.1
Others	19	15.7

Table 4: Education Levels of Victims

Variable Category	N	%	
Religion			
Christianity	45	37.0	
Islam	64	53.0	
Traditional	8	6.7	
Others	4	3.3	
Others	22	18.1	
Marital Status	Single	59	49.0

4.4 Occupational Status of RTC Victims

The study shows that drivers were the most frequent road crash victims, accounting for 22% of respondents (Figure 1). This indicates that drivers may be at a higher risk due to their work involving prolonged exposure to traffic conditions. Civil servants and farmers were the second-largest group, thereby suggesting that road crashes have an impact on stable employment sectors like public service and agriculture. The unemployed accounted for 9% which shows that individuals not engaged in formal employment still face risks related to road safety. Students made up of 4.2%, less frequently involved in road traffic crashes. The remaining categories include businessmen/women, professionals, private firm employees, manual labourers, and artisans that represent less than 10% of total respondents.

5 IMPACT ON HOUSEHOLDS

5.1 Hospitalisation Experiences of RTC Victims and Relatives

The result in the number of nights spent by both

RTC victims and relatives in Figure 2 shows that 33.9% of RTC victims indicated they spent between 1 to 7 days in the hospital, 20.6% remained hospitalised for 1 to 2 months, and 4.1% spent six months or more under care.

Figure 1: Occupational Status of RTC Victims
 Source: Authors' Field Survey (2025)

Figure 2: Number of Nights spent by RTC Victims and Relatives in the Hospital
 Source: Authors' Field Survey (2025)

5.2 Daily Expenses of RTC Victims and Relatives

The result of cost of treatment spent by RTC victims on a daily basis reveals that majority of victims (81%) reported daily treatment costs of less than ₦10,000 indicating relatively low financial burdens for most patients during their hospital stays (figure 3). However, the figure also raises concerns about the quality and extent of care received, as lower costs may correlate with limited resources available in healthcare settings. Also, the costs incurred by relatives for transportation, meals, gifts and other assistance reveals that 30.5% spent between ₦20,500 and ₦30,000, indicating a considerable financial burden associated with supporting victims during their recovery. This invariably shows that families face economic pressures in trying to provide care and support during challenging times relating to RTCs.

Figure 3: Daily Spending by RTC Victims and Relatives for Hospitalization
 Source: Authors' Field Survey (2025)

Table 5: Impact of RTCs on Victims and Relatives

Variable	Frequency	(%)
Impact on Victims		
Very Low	-	-
Low	7	5.7
Medium	-	-
High	43	35.6
Very High	71	58.7
Impact on Relatives		
Loss of sources of	17	14
Loss of time at the	35	29
Out of job	24	19
Out of school	15	13
Loss of material	22	18.4
Others	8	6.6
Level of Impact on Relatives		
Very Low	2	1.6
Low	3	2.5
Medium	6	5
High	67	55.4
Very High	43	35.5

Source Authors' Field Survey (2025)

5.4 Intervention and Support for RTC Victims

The analysis of road traffic crash (RTC) victims' hospitalisations reveals that Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) were the most contributors, providing support to 44% of victims, followed by private individuals at 28%, as presented in Figure 4. Public sector support was relatively low at 8%. The majority of support was in the form of material assistance, accounting for 60%, with cash support being the least at only 12%. This shows the critical role of NGOs in supporting RTC victims and the need for diverse forms of assistance, particularly material support, to aid recovery efforts effectively.

Figure 4: Supporting Sectors and Types of Intervention Received by RTC Victims

Source Authors' Field Survey (2025)

5.5 Estimation of the Socioeconomic Costs of RTCs

Direct and Indirect Cost

Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs) are a global socioeconomic challenge with significant impacts on public health, economic productivity, and social welfare. The costs associated with RTCs are assessed using the costing principles of European COST313 comprising both direct and indirect methods. Direct costs include medical, administrative, funeral, and property damage, while indirect costs include productivity losses, long-term care costs, and impacts on families and communities. The study assessed the direct and indirect costs of road traffic crashes (RTCs) in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) using the human capital approach. The socio-economic costs of RTCs in 2022 was estimated at ₦534.9 billion, equivalent to approximately US\$1.2 billion, as presented in Table 6. This figure is a conservative lower bound estimates based on underreported figures about casualties and incidents in the study area. This clearly shows the growing socioeconomic burden imposed by road traffic crashes in the FCT.

The analysis of the direct financial costs of road traffic crashes (RTCs) in FCT reveals that crashes cause financial strain, amounting to approximately ₦5.2 billion, accounting for 1% of the total socio-economic burden.

Table 6: Costs of Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs) in the FCT for the Year 2022

Costs	Unit cost (₦)	Total cost	
		In Naira (₦)	In US Dollars (US\$)
<i>Direct Costs</i>			
Medical costs	37,700.10/day	2,322,120,000.00	5,160,266.67
Hospital stays	18,500.30/day	1,161,078,828.00	2,580,175.17
Hospital visitation	15,300.00/day	960,228,000.00	2,133,840.00
Transportation	12,800.00/day	803,328,000.00	1,785,173.33
Sub-Total		5,246,754,828.00	11,659,455.17
<i>Non-Healthcare cost</i>			
FRSC operations	-	551,767,000.00	1,226,148.89
Administrative costs	86,224,137.00	1,038,689,640.00	2,308,199.20
Property damage	-	711,696,180.00	1,581,547.07
Sub-Total		2,302,152,820.00	5,115,895.16
<i>Indirect Costs</i>			
Hospitalization	10,500.00/day	786,240,000.00	1,747,200.00
Funeral cost	-	47,674,000.00	105,942.22
Production costs	2,343,750,000.00	526,500,000,000.00	1,170,000,000.00
Human costs	₦53,250.00	33,228,000.00	73,840.00
Sub-Total		527,367,142,000.00	1,171,926,982.00
Total costs		534,916,049,648.00	1,188,702,333.00

Source: Authors' Field Work (2025)

The costs include medical expenses for injured individuals, hospital admissions, and transportation costs. Non-healthcare costs, including operational expenses for the Federal Road Safety Corps, property damage, and insurance and administrative fees which account for 0.4% of the overall financial impact.

Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs) in FCT cause a financial burden which is estimated at ₦527.3 billion, accounting for 98.6% of the total economic impact. This includes post-emergency hospitalization expenses, lost productivity due to extended stays, and mobility-related economic losses. The fiscal consequences demand the need for targeted interventions and policy reforms to address public health and economic challenges.

Non-Monetary Market Costs

The study examines road traffic crashes (RTCs) in terms of human and production costs, revealing significant economic implications. The financial burden associated with RTCs, were assessed considering both human costs and production losses due to fatalities and injuries.

Human cost estimation

The WTP method estimates the monetary value that individuals assign to reducing the risk of Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs). As shown in Table 7, the monthly willingness to pay (WTP) for 198

Table 7: Estimating Human cost of RTC victims using WTP method

Question	Number of cases	Mean in Naira	Median in Naira
Monthly Willingness-to-pay	198	7,000	693,000
Bi-monthly Willingness-to-pay	26	12,000	156,000
Quarterly Willingness-to-pay	15	10,000	75,000
Annual Willingness-to-pay	12	17,000	102,000
The marginal value of Human cost per victim/ year	₦53,250.00 x 624 = ₦33,228,000.00		

Source: Authors' Field Work (2025)

Cost of Production Loss Estimation

The production loss due to RTCs is substantial. In 2022, the total cases of RTC were 624, in which fatalities cases were 101, and injuries (523). Based on life expectancy of 55.5 years, given value of statistical life = \$50,000/year, the overall cost of production lost due to RTCs is estimated at \$1.17 billion, which translates to approximately ₦526.5 billion when converted at an exchange rate of 450 Naira (as at time of survey) per US Dollars in Table 8

Table 8: Cost of production loss to Victims as a result of RTCs in the FCT

Year	Total cases	No. of fatalities	No. of injuries	Life expectancy	Value of Statistical life	Overall cost of production lost
2022	624	101	523	55.5	\$50,000/year	US\$1,170,000,000.00 (₦526,500,000.00)

Source: Authors' Field Work (2025)

The analysis shows that the human cost associated with RTCs is significant but relatively lower than the production losses. The overall economic impact of RTCs in terms of lost production far exceeds the human cost estimates derived from WTP. This indicates that while individual willingness to pay reflects a personal valuation for safety and risk reduction, the broader economic implications (especially regarding productivity losses) indicates the urgent need for effective traffic safety measures and policies to address these issues to save both human and economic losses.

The overall human cost derived from these values is estimated at ₦2,052,000 for the reported cases. Moreover, the marginal value of human cost per victim

Human cost estimation

The WTP method estimates the monetary value that individuals assign to reducing the risk of Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs). As shown in Table 7, the monthly willingness to pay (WTP) for 198 cases is calculated with a mean value of ₦7,000, resulting in a total of ₦1,386,000. The bi-monthly WTP for 26 cases, at a mean of ₦12,000, totals ₦312,000. The quarterly WTP for 15 cases, with a mean of ₦10,000, amounts to ₦150,000. However, the annual WTP for 12 cases, which has a mean of ₦17,000, totals ₦204,000 per year is estimated at ₦53,250, which leads to a total annual human cost of approximately ₦33,228,000 when extrapolated for 624 cases.

Costs of Preventing RTCs in the FCT

Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs) pose a public safety concern and necessitate a comprehensive approach that encompasses both proactive and reactive strategies. Proactive measures—including public education initiatives, enhanced law enforcement strategies, and engineering improvements—are vital during the pre-crash phase. The estimated cost of interventions by the Federal Road Safety Corps (FRSC) to prevent RTCs in the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) is ₦211.7 million (US\$151,266.57), which constitutes 9.4% of the overall budget (see Table 9).

Law enforcement expenditures are projected at ₦1.9 billion (US\$1.3 million), making up 85.1% of the budget. Engineering interventions are estimated to require ₦121.7 million (US\$86,950.00), representing the smallest allocation at 5.5%. In total, approximately ₦2.2 billion (US\$1.6 million) is essential for the effective management and mitigation of road traffic crashes in the FCT.

Table 9: Estimated Costs of Preventing RTCs in the FCT in a Year

Activity	Cost per month (₦)	Total costs on yearly	
		(₦)	(US\$)
<i>Public Education</i>			
Print media such as Newspapers and Magazines	105,570.00	1,266,840.00	904.89
Electronic media such as Radio and Television	274,400.00	3,292,800.00	2,352.00
Printing of booklets, pamphlets, fliers, leaflets, stickers and banners (for billboards)	214,000	2,568,000.00	1,834.29
Visits to Schools, Churches and Mosques	275,000.00	3,300,000.00	2,357.14
Motor-park rallies using PA system, canopies, tables/chairs, generator and caravans	1,358,500.00	16,302,000.00	11,644.29
Salaries of FRSC staff (42)	6,048.000	72,576,000.00	51,840.00
Vehicles (7) + Fuelling & Maintenance	113, 734,400.00	113,734,400.00	81,238.86
Sub- Total		211,773,200.00	151,266.57
<i>Enforcement</i>			
Salaries of FRSC staff (475)	68,400,000.00	820,800,000.00	586,285.71
Vehicles (27) + Fuelling & Maintenance	-	615,920,000.00	439,942.86
Power Bike (27) +Fuelling & Maintenance	-	415,360,000.00	296,685.71
Enforcement using radar guns, breathalysers, weight bridges, binocular, wheel lock, patrollites, binocular, VHF(Radio) Walkie-Talkie and reflective jackets	-	56,487,000.00	40,347.86
Sub-Total		1,908,567,000.00	1,363,262.14
<i>Engineering</i>			
Road Audit and Inspection (Working materials such as pens, pencils, notebooks, plain sheets, sketch pads and report files).	32,000.00	2,688,000.00	1,920.00
Camera for photography	310,000.00	310,000.00	221.43
Salaries of FRSC staff (17)	2,448,000.00	29,376,000.00	20,982.86
Vehicles (7) +Fuelling & Maintenance	-	89,356,000.00	63,825.71
Sub-Total		121,730,000.00	86,950.00
Grand Total		2,242,070,200.00	1,601,478.71

Source: Authors' fieldwork 2024

6 DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The study examined the socioeconomic costs of Road Traffic Crashes (RTCs) in FCT Abuja, Nigeria, which provided insights into its social and economic impacts on victims and their supporting families. The research reveals a clear gender disparity among victims. This predominance of the male gender is attributed to riskier driving behaviour and greater exposure to traffic environment. The age distribution also indicates that middle-aged individuals were most affected in this context.

The analysis of income characteristics reveals that a considerable proportion of RTC victims came from low-income backgrounds. This economic status and vulnerability exacerbates the financial strain caused by RTCs, thereby limiting access to essential medical care and rehabilitation services. In the same vein, educational disparities were similarly evident, correlating with broader socioeconomic challenges that impede recovery and long-term economic stability.

The experiences of hospitalization reveal diverse recovery needs. A good percentage of relatives encountered economic burdens due to the time spent supporting victims during their recovery process. The study estimates the socioeconomic costs of RTCs in the FCT to be approximately N534.9 billion (around US\$1.2 billion) in 2022, emphasizing the extensive financial implications that extend beyond immediate medical expenses. However, the importance of NGOs in providing support is elaborated during the study. This calls for diverse support systems that will adequately address both material and financial needs of RTC victims during the recovery phase. The results corroborate the findings of [Azmi](#) and [Ram](#) (2023) that revealed that Road Traffic Crashes generate substantial personal and national losses.

The socioeconomic impact of road traffic crashes (RTCs) in FCT Abuja require urgent and multifaceted strategies to mitigate. The huge financial burden, coupled with the long-term challenges faced by victims and families necessitated the need for systemic reform. Policymakers should prioritize road safety by strengthening road safety regulations, implementing comprehensive educational/enlightenment programmes for drivers, and establishing robust health support systems which are tailored to the needs of RTC victims. Ultimately, confronting the public health crisis caused by RTCs is not solely about enhancing road safety; it is a vital step towards promoting social equity and ensuring the well-being of all citizens in Nigeria.

7. ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND APPROVAL

The FCT Health Research Ethics Committee (FCT HREC) approved the research in the selected General Hospitals of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT) which was granted under reference number FHREC/2023/01/48/03-14-23. Similarly, the Federal Road Safety Corps released RTC data for these studies vide reference numbers FRSC/HQ/PRS/522/VOLIV/023. This research adhered to ethical standards and guidelines as mandated by the National Health Research Ethics Committee (NHREC) of Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Azmi, A.A. and Ram, S. (2023). *Accident Victim Characteristics and Identification of Key Parameters for Compensation in Indian Context*. Journal of Urban Planning and Transport Research. 11,(1). Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1080/21650020.2023.2235418>. Accessed online on 25th April, 2024
- Donário, A. A., Santos, R. B. D., & Elvik, R. (2012). The economic and social cost of road accidents: the portuguese case. *The economic and social cost of road accidents: the portuguese case*.
- Eke, A. A. S. (2015). Compensation of the Driver as a Motor Accident Victim in Cameroon: A Critical Appraisal of the Cima Code. *Open Journal of Social Sciences*, 3(8), 144-161.
- ETSC (2007). A Methodological Approach to National Road Safety Policies. European Transport Safety Council, Brussels. <https://etsc.eu/wp-content/upload/social-and-economic-consequences-of-road-traffic-injury-in-Europe>
- FRSC (2016). Nigerian Highway Code: Road User's Handbook. Federal Road Safety Corps. Printed by Detailworks. Abuja.
- Huang, L., Adhikary, K. P., Choulagai, B. P., Wang, N., Poudyal, A. K., & Onta, S. R. (2016). Road Traffic Accident and its Characteristics in Kathmandu Valley. *Journal of the Nepal Medical Association*, 55(203).
- Huang, L. (2024). Human Capital and Economic Growth in Fujian Province-China. *Economics, Finance and Management Review*, 3 (19), 4-13.
- Mohammad I.A. & Abdelmageed, S. M. (2010). Cost of road traffic accidents in Egypt. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 4(6), 1219-1225.

- Sung N.M & Rios M. (2015). Road Crashes have more Impact on Poverty than You probably thought. *Transport for Development*. <https://blogs.worldbank.org/transport/road-crashes-have-more-impact-poverty-you-probably-thought>
- Takako, T. (2019). State Of Damage to and Support for Victims of Motor Vehicle Accidents in Japan. *IATSS Research*. 43, 97-107. Accessed on 4th Nov, 2021.
- Uhegbu, U.N. and Tight, R. M. (2021). Road User Attitudes and Their Reported Behaviours in Abuja, Nigeria. *Sustainability MDPI*, 13, 4222.
- UN (2018). *World Urbanization Prospect 2018*. Department of Economic and Social Affairs. Population Division. United Nations, New York. <https://population.un.org/wup/>.
- WHO (2018). *Road Traffic Injuries*. World Health Organisation. WHO Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen, Denmark.
- WHO (2021). *WHO Kick off Decade of Action for Road Safety*. World Health Organization, Geneva. www.decadeofaction.org
- Yang, B. M., & Kim, J. (2003). Road traffic accidents and policy interventions in Korea. *Injury control and safety promotion*, 10(1-2), 89-94.
- Yang, B. M., & Kim, J. (2003). Road traffic accidents and policy interventions in Korea. *Injury control and safety promotion*, 10(1-2), 89-94.
- Takako, T. (2019). State Of Damage to and Support for Victims of Motor Vehicle Accidents in Japan. *IATSS Research*. 43, 97-107. Accessed on 4th Nov, 2021.
- Uhegbu, U.N. and Tight, R. M. (2021). Road User Attitudes and Their Reported Behaviours in Abuja, Nigeria. *Sustainability MDPI*, 13, 4222.